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PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF LEARNING CHEMISTRY FOR LEARNERS AND TEACHERS

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Abstract

The New Education Policy (1986) sought to involve teachers in defining and sharing effective teaching-learning practices. However, from a political perspective, educational progress across the curriculum was far too slow and uneven. Government framed and revised policy time to time to include teachers for various activities of national and curriculum importance. This forced a considerable reduction of flexibility and autonomy (and enjoyment) and a loss of available time and energy, because of much enhanced accountability and curriculum pressure.

Objectives - It was particularly significant since this inhibits teachers' engagement in research, development or even in reflective practices in their own classrooms. Scoring students' hundred percent result on the basis of mugging up the contents, can establish a teacher as qualified or effective or best? This paper is trying to provide a detailed specification of teachers' necessary science knowledge. Teachers differ from scientists, not necessarily in the quality or quantity of their subject matter knowledge, but in how that knowledge is organized and used. The focus of educational research is very heavily weighted towards conceptions of students, implicitly assuming that chemistry teachers know the right scientific answers for each and every problem. There is, of course no argument for careless reasoning or sloppy vocabulary, but surely it is part of any pattern of careful thinking that meanings and significance of words and ideas are constantly re-evaluated? What is unique about the teaching process is that it requires teachers to transform their subject matter knowledge for the purpose of teaching.

Design/ Methodology/Approach - Uncertainty, ambiguity and fuzziness are inevitable and an integral part of the epistemology of chemistry. There is a statement about people's understandings of science that there is no single knowledge gap between scientists and non-scientists, but there is, instead, a multitude of specific gaps between specialists and non-

specialists in each field. Pedagogical content knowledge is highly specific to the concepts being taught, is much more than just subject matter knowledge alone and develops over time as a result of teaching experience.

Findings - Pedagogical content knowledge is highly specific to the concepts being taught, is much more than just subject matter knowledge alone and develops over time as a result of teaching experience. A Chemistry teacher evolves or establishes only if the any expert critically reflects on and interprets the subject matter; finds multiple ways to represent the information as analogies, metaphors, examples, problems, demonstrations, and/or classroom activities; adapts the material to students' developmental levels and abilities, gender, prior knowledge and misconceptions and finally tailors the material to those specific individual or groups of students to whom the information will be taught.

Limitations – Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary and inferential conclusions. The research could have been more valuable if it has been included more examples and conclusions.

Practical Implications – This paper can encourage, inspire and experts of the subject Chemistry for bringing certain changes in their existing teaching and learning strategies for better future. By implementing better teaching-learning process for chemistry, the environments can become more competitive.

Originality/Value – This paper include practical examples to include, justify and sustain chemistry teaching to enhance learning for better adaptability in the new and recent environments. It promotes the unique and interesting approach.

Keywords: Pedagogy, Chemistry, Teaching, Learning, Conceptions, Curriculum, Science, Knowledge,

1. Introduction

The New Education Policy (1986) sought to involve teachers in defining and sharing effective teaching-learning practices. However, from a political perspective, educational progress across the curriculum was far too slow and uneven. From years, there had been political and public concerns about educational provisions and standards. These concerns centered on a perceived lack of rigour in the school curriculum and the diverse provision in the schools. For science education, this policy was significant in making science compulsory for all pupils.

Moving to compulsory science for all has provided a more balanced diet for learners. Jenkins (2000) and Donnelly (2000) provide insight that science teachers have of their roles in framing and implementation of the curriculum. Government framed and revised policy time to time to include teachers for various activities of national and curriculum importance. This forced a considerable reduction of flexibility and autonomy (and enjoyment) and a loss of available time and energy, because of much enhanced accountability and curriculum pressure. It was particularly significant since this inhibits teachers' engagement in research, development or even in reflective practices in their own classrooms. These new governmental constraints have also spread to teacher education and training. Those responsible for the educational system seem to see science education as a repository of certainty and *getting it right* as the main prerequisite for science teachers. They also seem to see learning as a relatively unproblematic or mechanistic process that requires only clarity from the teacher and sufficient hard work on the part of the student, for the material presented to be learned. It is sufficient for a learner to qualify any examination but is it sufficient for a learner to understand what he or she is doing or learning? Scoring students' hundred percent result on the basis of mugging up the contents, can establish a teacher as qualified or effective or best? This paper is trying to provide a detailed specification of teachers' necessary science knowledge.

2. Literature Review

According to Driver and Easley (1978), Bodner (1986), Nakhleh (1992) and Garnett et al. (1995) that much has been written about constructivism in Chemistry and the ways in which learners make sense by constructing meanings and explanations for themselves. However, of greater concern is the relative lack of impact that most research into chemistry learning has had on the practice of chemistry education in schools and university classrooms and the very small numbers of practicing teachers who have an interest in educational research (de Jong 1999).

3. Pedagogical Content Knowledge

Pedagogical content knowledge is a type of knowledge that is unique to teachers and is based on the manner in which teachers relate their pedagogical knowledge (how to teach) to their subject matter knowledge (what to teach). It is a form of knowledge that projects science teachers as teachers rather than scientists (Gudmundsdottir and Shulman 1987). Teachers differ

from scientists, not necessarily in the quality or quantity of their subject matter knowledge, but in how that knowledge is organized and used. Cochran et al. (1993) revised Shulman's original model to a model that results from an integration of four major components; Subject matter knowledge, Pedagogical knowledge, Knowledge of students' abilities and learning strategies and Subject matter expert with mode and concepts clarity.

A topic of *Photosynthesis* can be taught differently by different Educators. *Physical chemist* will see more of physics in it. *Inorganic chemist* will stress on water and nutrients and *Organic chemist* will stress for energy and various forms of compounds formed. *Biologist* may stress more on physiology but may forget to tell about chemistry behind that. *Physicist* may try to find physics laws behind that. Little or inappropriate knowledge, understanding and attitude lead to misconceptions. The topic photosynthesis may have different values for different experts but the learner needs one and comprehensive approach. Carpenter et al. (1988), Feiman-Nemser and Parker (1990) and Gess-Newsome and Lederman (1993) mention that novice or inexperienced teachers tend to make broad pedagogical decisions without assessing students' prior knowledge, ability levels, or learning strategies because they are not expert in content fields and base teaching decisions. Research is needed to find the appropriate methodology to make students understand the contents properly and accurately.

The focus of educational research is very heavily weighted towards conceptions of students, implicitly assuming that chemistry teachers know the right scientific answers for each and every problem. While teaching a lesson or writing a book, when such people demonstrate alternative conceptions, these *mistakes* are simple deprecated. It is not mentioned to highlight such people but it is argued here that we all carry with us facets of basic chemical knowledge that may not pass muster when subjected to critical examination by others. This is inevitable and however much one strives for absolute correctness at whatever level some uncertainty will remain. Even after going through very careful preparation for writing an article or presenting a teaching session there can be no absolute assurance that everything will be correct.

Uncertainty, ambiguity and fuzziness are inevitable and an integral part of the epistemology of chemistry. Certainly students need to accept that *sense making* is integral to the doing and learning of chemistry. This is why educators should try to use words carefully, define terms, state laws as clearly as possible and continually match and rematch these ideas with experience and the ideas of others. Science (chemistry) education is being pushed towards

greater certainty, greater emphasis on test and examination scores, greater bureaucratic accountability and less flexibility, autonomy and professional satisfaction (and fun) for science teachers and their students - all in the name of higher standards.

Perhaps there was too little certainty and consistency during earlier times but we now seem to be losing balance in the opposite direction. Some uncertainty legitimates, indeed requires questioning, contribution, debate, invention and ideas from teachers and students. Too much uncertainty or certainty will make science (chemistry) too complex, difficult to learn and impossible to teach. Wong (2001) considered an appropriate flavour of uncertainty for the health of science (chemistry) to be good.

4. Discussion

There is a statement about people's understandings of science that there is no single knowledge gap between scientists and non-scientists, but there is, instead, a multitude of specific gaps between specialists and non-specialists in each field. Surely all scientists should agree on the meaning of basic words in our vocabulary? Unfortunately it seems that this can never be the case since our words carry with them our interpretations, experiences, beliefs and sometimes even our emotions. When others receive the same words it is their meanings they hear. Words do not restrict their meanings to one particular definition even if there is a meaning carrying the IUPAC endorsement. It is necessary that the words have the same meanings, especially when considering exchanges between novice learners (students) and more experienced learners (teachers). It does not really matter whether neutralization is a redox reaction or whether carbonated drinks boil when poured into a glass. That is unless the belief of teacher/examiner differs markedly from learners. This provides pressure for students to learn (and be taught) right answers that do not necessarily make sense. The key concern here is that we learn to tolerate that there can never be a uniform set of meanings for words within the scientific community. We must expect meanings to develop and be prepared to renegotiate meanings as we learn. There is, of course no argument for careless reasoning or sloppy vocabulary, but surely it is part of any pattern of careful thinking that meanings and significance of words and ideas are constantly re-evaluated? It is not helpful in the long term to learn meaningless words by rote. This relates to the wider issue of teacher competence. The competence required is an ability and confidence to,

not only present science to their students, but also to contend science with their students (Goodwin 2000). This is necessary to have:

- ✓ Proper justification for its place in the curriculum.
- ✓ For society and individual students.
- ✓ An appropriate balance between passing examinations and learning science.
- ✓ A continuing enthusiasm for learning by the teacher.
- ✓ The critical engagement of students.
- ✓ To develop students' autonomy in learning.

The teachers require a robust and consistent story of science for themselves but it must remain legitimate for them to be continually learning and not to have known before they began teaching. What is unique about the teaching process is that it requires teachers to *transform* their subject matter knowledge for the purpose of teaching (Shulman, 1986). Pedagogical content knowledge is highly specific to the concepts being taught, is much more than just subject matter knowledge alone and develops over time as a result of teaching experience.

5. Conclusion

The science (chemistry) being learned by any individual is at the boundary of their experience and, if it is to be useful it must be significant and make some kind of sense. Teachers themselves gain insights by learning with their students and this requires mutual respect of ideas as well as continuous critical evaluation in both directions. Questioning and uncertainty must be legitimate within the framework and development of national guidelines, syllabuses, programs of assessment and patterns of qualification. It is a 'question of balance', but it seems that if we are to make progress in becoming scientists or doing science - and perhaps even in remaining human - nothing must ever be quite certain. A Chemistry teacher evolves or establishes only if the any expert critically reflects on and interprets the subject matter; finds multiple ways to represent the information as analogies, metaphors, examples, problems, demonstrations, and/or classroom activities; adapts the material to students' developmental levels and abilities, gender, prior knowledge and misconceptions and finally tailors the material to those specific individual or groups of students to whom the information will be taught.

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